

1 The norovirus infection transcriptome.

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7
8 Diarrheal diseases can be inflammatory or infectious. We recently described the rotavirus transcriptome
9 in the blood and in the small intestine. Here we measured total transcription in human jejunal organoids *in*
10 *vitro* following infection with norovirus to understand the largest transcriptome changes associated with
11 norovirus infection in the gastrointestinal tract. Interferon pathway activation was widespread and included
12 induction of *Ifit2* and *Ifit3* and *OASL*. *Herc5* and *Herc6* E3 ligases were activated by norovirus infection, as
13 was *Cmpk2* indicating nucleotide metabolic changes as a consequence of rotavirus and norovirus
14 infection. We describe activation of a nuclear factor *Zc3hav1* as a specific consequence of infection with a
15 colitogenic virus. Norovirus infection silenced CCL28 production and activated IL-6R. We provide
16 molecular evidence for autophagic dysfunction resulting from norovirus infection in human cells.

17 Citations

18 1. Marchiando, A.M., Ramanan, D., Ding, Y., Gomez, L.E., Hubbard-Lucey, V.M., Maurer, K., Wang,
19 C., Ziel, J.W., Van Rooijen, N., Nuñez, G. and Finlay, B.B., 2013. A deficiency in the autophagy gene
20 Atg16L1 enhances resistance to enteric bacterial infection. *Cell host & microbe*, 14(2), pp.216-224.

21 2. Matsuzawa-Ishimoto, Y.U., Shono, Y., Gomez, L.E., Hubbard-Lucey, V.M., Cammer, M., Neil, J.,
22 Dewan, M.Z., Lieberman, S.R., Lazrak, A., Marinis, J.M. and Beal, A., 2017. Autophagy protein ATG16L1
23 prevents necroptosis in the intestinal epithelium. *Journal of Experimental Medicine*, 214(12),
24 pp.3687-3705.

25
26
27
28
GSE183223